

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

SUPPLY & VALUE CHAIN FORUM

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PAPERS

OWC 2021 - Supply & Value Chain Forum

MULTISTAKEHOLDERS INITIATIVES

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-1077

THE CONCEPT OF MULTI-STAKEHOLDER-PARTNERSHIP IN AQUACULTURE SHRIMP VALUE CHAINS AS A BASE FOR MANGROVE PROTECTION IN BANGLADESH AND INDIA

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Summary: The mangrove forests of tropical coasts belong to the world's most important ecosystems and are disappearing at an alarming rate due to human activities. One of the major reasons thereof is the rapid expansion of commercial shrimp aquaculture in Southeast Asia. The aim of our project is to establish a multi-stakeholder dialogue on both sides of the shrimp value chain, i.e. in Europe as well as in India and Bangladesh as target countries.

These dialogues are dealing with the issues of mangrove-friendly (e.g. organic) shrimp aquaculture development and aiming to connect the views and realities of small-scale farmers, processors, exporters, importers, retailers, scientists, civil society, and the governmental bodies. The format our project is the so-called Multi-Stakeholder-Partnership (MAP). This approach aims to create mutual understanding and joint planning towards a common goal, i.e. the preservation and restoration of mangrove forests in the shrimp farming environment.

During the project, several concrete pilot-scale measures are implemented as case-studies, referring to (1) mangrove protection and restoration (e.g. regarding harmonisation of legislative processes), (2) the farming practice, particularly demonstration farms and training centres dealing with integrated mangrove aquaculture, and (3) improvements of the value chain (e.g. cold stores for the farmers' communities).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Aquaculture, Mangrove Protection, Multi-Stakeholder-Partnership, Transformative Process, Value Chain

Topic 1 - Experiences and innovations for a continuous improvement in reducing the environmental impacts of the production processes

OWC2020-SUP-1342

CIRCULAR ECONOMY INITIATIVES TO MAXIMIZE THE VALUE OF ORGANIC FOOD

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Summary: Food is lost or wasted throughout the supply chain, from initial agricultural production down to final household consumption. This paper highlights possible ways to improve the efficiency of the food supply and consumption chains by Leezen Company. Founded in 1998, it is the largest grocery chain of organic and natural foods in Taiwan committed to maximizing the value of organic food.

In a concerted approach, the Company improves coordination between different actors in the supply chain to address food losses and waste. Several strategies Leezen implements to save food include the development of new products from surplus crops, food redistribution programmes, raising-awareness initiatives and alternative use of products.

Moreover, Leezen plays an important role in tackling food waste by facilitating closed-loop models so that losses or waste of all forms are fed to the extent possible back into the value chain such as finding beneficial use for safe food that is presently thrown away.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: chain, circular, economy, food, innovative, supply

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-832

THE KEYS TO REINE MATHILDE'S SUCCESS, A DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM FOR THE ORGANIC DAIRY SECTOR

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Summary: Faced with the worldwide optimistic growth trend in organic farming, the food chains are getting structured to ensure the supply. In this context a question arises: how can we support the transition from conventional to organic agriculture while respecting the foundations of organic farming in a sustainable way?

For 9 years the Reine Mathilde program has been building and maintaining this breeding ground to the development of organic farming by involving all the actors of the sector concerned in a given territory and providing free access to all its actions and publications.

The varied actions aim to benefit all the targets that participate in the ecosystem of the sector (producers, advisers, vets, academics...). This collaborative dynamic also contributes to homogenize and raise the overall level of skills of the partners involved in the program. This new and complete partnership model, for a common, collective and open source project, maximizes synergies and multiplies the benefits.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: dairy production, development, Multi-Stakeholder-Partnership, multi-techniques, open source, programme

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-885

TAIWAN TEA INDUSTRY VALUE CHAIN - A CASE STUDY OF “TEA TALENT”

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Summary: Agricultural enterprises with strong belief in organic cultivation can support the concept and development of organic cultivation because of their own funds and professional technology.

Starting from the demand side, through excellent cultivation technology and tea making technology, organic production and consumers are linked. And the concept of sustainable ecology can also affect the willingness of farmers around to adopt organic cultivation because of the success of brand building.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: organic agriculture, tea industry, value chain

Topic 2 - A life-oriented paradigm to foster the organic movements

OWC2020-CUL-1398

AGRO - ECONOMY AND COMMONS - A CONCEPT FOR VIABLE AGRICULTURAL STRUCTURES

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Summary: Agriculture uses and consumes common goods: land, water, air, landscape, biodiversity. However, sustainable agriculture and organic farming in particular is able of produce, maintain and to increase the value and the diversity of these common goods. Due to a close focus on the micro-economy of the farm, it is obvious to externalise the costs for the commons as far as possible.

So, microeconomic profit impacts the economy of the commons. With transfer payments, the public sector tries to finance several biodiversity and ecosystem services with taxpayers' money. However, this creates heavy dependencies on politics and weakens entrepreneurship of farmers.

In this paper, a concept will be proposed that allows a restructuration of an agricultural enterprise to manage both conditions, the current market-economic framework and the long-term sustainable common goods.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Accounting, Commons, Economy, non profit, True cost accounting

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1013

BUILDING ORGANIC AND FAIR-TRADE SUPPLY CHAINS FROM PRODUCERS TO CONSUMERS

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Summary: BIOPARTENAIRE® is the organic fair trade label that certifies French as well as international supply chains. Both producers and processors are involved in its governance.

In October 2019, the National Syndicate of Organic Retailers (Synadis Bio) will join the Biopartenaire association as a non-certified partner member. In 2020, collaboration on retailers' commitments in organic fair trade supply chains will be carried on. As the final link of the chain, they are in contact with consumers and act as ambassadors for the global quality of the products they sell.

They play a key role in developing conscious, sustainable consumption. Their commitments toward companies are also important to secure outlets for partner producers. We intend to share the result of this work at the IFOAM congress.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Biopartenaire, commitments, Fair Trade, label, retailers

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1428

4 PROPOSITIONS OF THE "BIOVALEURS" (ORGANIC VALUES) THINK TANK TO BETTER SHARE VALUE ALONG ORGANIC SUPPLY CHAINS

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Summary: Convinced by the effectiveness of their model but also aware of its fragility in the face of dominant models and lobbies, companies and entrepreneurs precursors of the Organic sector have decided to pool their experiences to question the best way to ensure the long-term success of the Organic model and its founding values.

These leading companies (BIOCOOP, PRONATURA, ARCADIE, ECOCERT, BELLEDONNE, BIOLAIT, LEA NATURE, LSDH, TRIBALLAT NOYAL, NUTRITION & HEALTH), with varied structures (family businesses, SCOP, Cooperatives ...) represent 50% of the organic market in France and are present at all stages of the organic food chain, from farmers to distributors and certifiers. They are all represented within BIOVALEURS by their directors in order to establish a top-to-top dialogue with influencers and policy makers.

In 2017, they created BIOVALEURS (<https://biovaleurs.fr/>), an independent and transversal think-tank with the aim of bringing together personalities recognized for their commitment or that of the structures they represent and of working together on solutions that will enable the development of a consistent organic sector respectful of the founding values.

To defend the values of organic farming, the Biovaleurs think tank worked on proposals to ensure that organic farming creates economic, social, environmental and societal wealth, shared with all and that it preserves its historical and fundamental values.

The solutions to better share value along supply chains, in order to obtain fair trade organic products and improve working conditions operate at different levels: completely upstream for a better organization of supply chains in order to defend fair prices, at the regulatory level to regulate negotiation and contractualization practices, at the level of public policies and regulations, by strengthening specialized distribution channels that have a more partnership approach with their suppliers, at the very end of the value chain with consumer choice power.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Fair Trade, Governance, label, PUBLIC POLICIES, Value Chains, Social purpose

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-699

ORGANICS 3.0 PARTNERSHIPS: HOW TO ACCELERATE THE AGRICULTURAL TRANSITION IN TIMES OF FARMERWASHING?

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Summary: In a growing market for “local” and “farm-to-fork” food products, supermarkets and FMCG brands increasingly highlight these two aspects of a marginal fraction of their product range.

These disproportionate marketing efforts raise the competitive pressure for Alternative Food Networks. How to better differentiate the latter and simultaneously step up the transition towards Organic and Sustainable Food Systems?

This contribution argues that: i) “direct” food sales and “fair” prices do not match retailers’ commercial interests, ii) little or no trustworthy guarantee mechanisms exist for these value claims in conventional distribution channels, iii) embracing the Organics 3.0 vision, structural collaboration between the organic movement and the AFN presents an important opportunity to both grow the impact of these SFSC initiatives and gradually engage more farmers into a demand-driven transition. A case study of The Food Assembly provides insight on how this can materialise in practice.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Agroecological ladder, alternative food networks, Farmerwashing, Participatory Guarantee Systems, Short food supply chains, Transition

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-644

ORIENTATIONS AND POSITIONING OF SUPERMARKETS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS REGARDING TO CONSUMER EXPECTATIONS IN FRANCE

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Summary: Since the early 1990s, the supermarket chains have been involved in supporting the first nationwide initiatives to distribute organic agricultural products and have gradually stepped up their commitments to meet consumer expectations. The increase in the number of references, product ranges and partnerships with producers and their organizations has thus increased. Today, with 50% of the organic product market, the dynamic driver by the brands is focused on meeting the need of support for conversion, contractualization to correlate supply and demand and finally to preserve the specificities and requirement of the sector.

The FCD proposes to present the orientations and positioning of the distribution for the development of organic products regarding to consumer expectations.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Consumer expectations, contractualization, Retail, Supermarket

Topic 2 - A life-oriented paradigm to foster the organic movements

OWC2020-CUL-908

TRUSTWORTHINESS CHALLENGES AND PATHWAY TO FOSTER ORGANIC MOVEMENT IN BANGLADESH

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Summary: The organic farming practice still in unstructured stage in Bangladesh. Due to affluent consumer group has been growing at faster scale with health consciousness and thrive for safe food, the country has a huge market potential for organic produces. In the domestic market, the organic certification is not mandatory that puts the consumers in doubt on sources of organic produces.

Moreover, food adulteration situation of Bangladesh is very serious that pushes the consumers to get to know about organic produces what they are consuming. This paper emphasizes on two successful models that provides transparency of the organic supply chain that created information flow between consumers and producers with trustworthy manner.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Food adulteration, Knowledge, Organic produces, Transparency, Trustworthy

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1391

ORGANIC FOOD DIFFERENTIATION IN POPULAR MARKETS AND THEIR IMPACT ON LOW INCOME CONSUMERS

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Summary: After 3 years of work, the EcoConsumo Project executed by the AGRECOL Andes Foundation, concluded its project, reaching its objectives referred to, on the one hand, make visible the organic production in popular fairs, and on the other, sensitize the Cochabamba population about the advantages of responsible and ecological consumption.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: ecological food, low-income consumers, Market Access, purchase behaviour

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-995

BUILDING TRUST IN ORGANIC - HONG KONG EXPERIENCE

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Summary: Organic farming in Hong Kong has become the solution to tackle with the food safety problem due to the food scandals in mainland China. Wet mark survey in 2018 showed that 64% organic vegetables in the wet market were self-claimed organic.

29-78% and 20-100% of the local and mainland self-claimed organic vegetables contained pesticide exceeding the EU Maximum Residue Limits from 2016 to 2018, which explain the lack of confidence in organic produce in the wet markets.

Independent organic certification scheme has been developed to provide regulation for this unregulated market.

Hong Kong Organic Resource Centre has conducted confidence building measures such as promoting a creditable organic certification system, developing the unilateral product acceptance service, performing market surveillance and conducting education and awareness programme among various stakeholders in Hong Kong since 2005.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: None

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-958

"MARKET RESEARCH ABOUT THE PROFILE AND PURCHASING HABITS OF SANTOS CITY ORGANIC FAIRS CONSUMERS (SP/BRAZIL)"

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Summary: This is a Market Survey, via an online questionnaire, made with consumers who buy at organic fairs of Santos/SP/Brazil, to understand their profile, preferences, criticism and buying habits.

Market Research is a collection and interpretation of data and information that is transformed into knowledge.

The objective of this market research is to understand and analyze consumer perception of organic products, the reasons for buying (or not), preference for access channels, types of products consumed, frequency of purchase, degree of confidence in quality and inspection, criticism, needs, scope of the understanding of the environmental and social issue involving the organic food, etc.

Besides being a final work of IFOAM OLC-Brazil course (2017/2018), this report was sent to the Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture to promote actions in organic agriculture and environmental education to the population, and to use such research to guide public policies linked to these issues.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Consumer preferences, Habits, Marketing, organic fairs, PUBLIC POLICIES, Trends

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1369

ORGANIC AND FAIR TRADE – LOOKING BEYOND A HONEYMOON. EVIDENCE FROM THE NILGIRIS IN INDIA.

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Summary: The case study of Keystone Foundation, Last Forest Enterprises, and Aadhimalai in Tamil Nadu, India, showcases how a commitment to both organic and fair trade principles can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes. The co-authors present the opportunities and challenges, keeping in mind the different roles of value chain actors and the hurdles of marginalized communities in India's South.

Beyond the insights generated on the ground, the authors would like to discuss the case's implications for the joint development of organic and fair trade markets. In particular, they touch upon the practical shortcomings of organic agriculture in realizing social gains for producers on the ground, the entry points for fair trade and the nature of successful collaboration to achieve economic, social and ecological gains.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Fair Trade, India

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-238

HOW FAIR TRADE CAN CONTRIBUTE TO THE STRENGTHENING OF ORGANIC VALUE CHAINS? CASE STUDIES IN FRENCH DAIRY AND GRAIN AND PULSE CROP SECTOR

Julie Maisonhaute*¹, Christophe ALLIOT²

¹Commerce Équitable France, Nogent sur Marne, ²Le Basic, Paris, France

Summary: This study analyses the effects of fair trade partnerships for two organic farmer organisations in France: Biolait, a nation-wide milk collecting organisation (1300 farms), and Ferme de Chassagne, a group of 9 farms specialized in cereals and pulses. Both organisations have been set up by farmers in the 1990s in order to build market opportunities for organic products.

Both organisations have developed fair trade partnerships with brands and retailers, based on long term contracting and transparent price negotiations, with positive effects.

First, fair trade partnerships have helped to set collaborative negotiations among supply chain actors and build remunerative and guaranteed prices for farmers.

Second, these partnerships have supported the conversion of farmers to organic practices, and beyond towards agro-ecology and biodiversity enhancement. A central factor of success has been the strengthening of collective farmer organisations capable of developing independent strategies.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Conversion to organic, Dialogue in the value chain, Domestic fair trade, Farmer organisations, Remunerative price

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-722

HOW CAN AN ORGANIC DAIRY COMPANY USE FAIR-TRADE FRAMEWORK TO MAKE ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH FARMERS EVOLVE TO A VIRTUOUS MODEL EMBARKING RETAILERS AND CONSUMERS?

Antoine De Vaubernier¹

¹Les Prés Rient Bio, Saint Ouen, France

Summary: For 10 years Les Prés Rient Bio has been developing the volumes of organic milk collected in Normandy (France) in order to accompany the growth of its transformed dairy products. But meanwhile this small, local and autonomous subsidiary of Danone has been constantly fostering virtuous models for both farmers and consumers.

Today, Les Prés Rient Bio considers it is key to address a double challenge that the sector is facing : answer consumers expectations on social reassurance (on top of organic certification) ; and strengthen the economical resilience of farms in order to make sure there will be still farmers to collect in the years to come.

With such objective, Les Prés Rient Bio stretched its supply model using the fair-trade framework. The Fair For Life certification helped the company integrate strongly its 45 farmers and clients (retailers) in its value creation model, challenging the standard way of contractualizing.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Consumers, Fair Trade, Governance, milk, remunerative farming activity, retailers

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-847

FOREBIO'S PRIVATE STANDARDS, A SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A FAIR AND COHERENT AGRICULTURAL SYSTEM.

Laetitia Leray^{*1}, Jean-François Deglorie², Mathieu Lancry¹

¹Forebio, Paris, ²3 la Roussière, FOREBIO, Le Tablier, France

Summary: This contribution aims at presenting feedbacks of economical organizations of organic producers who decided to develop differentiation tools (different to public standards) to defend an agricultural system based on responsibility, transparency and coherence.

Knowing their initiatives and the impacts of these tools on the market, thanks to living examples, will demonstrate how organic transition could be accompanied and supported in future years.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: anticipation, collective assessment, ecological transition, organic specificities

Topic: How do we better share value along supply chains, how do we shift towards fair organic, and how do we improve working conditions?

OWC2021-SUP-1403

CSR AND FAIR TRADE: ORGANIC BUSINESSES COMMIT TO ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ORGANIC SUPPLY CHAINS

Auteur: Anna Kolf SYNABIO

Summary * With changes taking place in the organic agrifoods supply chain, and rising expectations for commitments from businesses, it's essential for organic players to get a head start and reaffirm their core values.

CSR approaches and fair-trade labels are complementary tools and cover all areas of sustainable development and supply chain-related issues. Fair working conditions, environmental protection, fair value distribution, support for farmers: with their complementarity, CSR and fair trade allow businesses to ensure better value distribution by offering fair products and taking measures to improve conditions for workers.

The question we would like to answer is: How can organic businesses leverage fair trade and CSR to help create sustainable organic networks?

We will be presenting two tools: Biopartenaire, a fair-trade standard, and BioED, a CSR standard, both of which are specific to the organic supply chain. Their shared roots and values make it possible to take into account the goals of the entire supply chain and to jointly create an organic sector that's consistent and meets demanding standards in all geographic regions.

In conclusion, we will explain how CSR and fair trade allow organic businesses to go beyond the requirements of their product specifications and to adopt a holistic approach to their operations.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility / Fair trade / supply chain / working conditions / value sharing / Fair trade and corporate social responsibility standards

SMALLHOLDERS PRODUCERS CHALLENGES: INTEGRITY AND EMPOWERMENT

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1004

GROWER GROUP CERTIFICATION - SHARED SURVEILLANCE AND REGIONAL ADAPTIVENESS UNDER INTERNATIONAL ORGANIC STANDARDS

Carolin Moeller*¹, Karen Mapusua²

¹Certification, NASAA Certified Organic, Stirling, Australia, ²SPC, Suva, Fiji

Summary: Group Certification is based on the concept of shared surveillance to ensure true compliance to organic standards and regulation. Group certification under organic regulations and standards was introduced as a certification product over 20 years ago.

In 2003 IFOAM International Organics set up the first guidelines on how to set up a grower group and its mandatory Internal Control System and how certification bodies shall certify these grower groups.

In 2019, certification bodies & grower groups called for reassessing procedures and evaluating potential of improvement for grower group's attainable certification requirements.

Driving factors

- global lack in traceability and true procedures in group certification
- compliance conflicts due to particular regional, socio-agricultural set ups of groups
- Approval for group certification within the EU

Through trialling training the need for regional adaptiveness of regulations/requirements has emerged

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Grower Groups, ICS Procedures on Sanctions and Inspections, Internal Control Systems, Pacifics, Regional organic standard, Shared Surveillance

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1231

PARTICIPATIVE ORGANIC CERTIFICATION IN THE CHAPINGO ORGANIC MARKET, MEXICO

Rita E. Schwentesius*¹, Rossa Cecilia Rodríguez Silva² and Laura Gómez Tovar and Miguel Octavio Villatoro

¹Chapingo Organic Market, Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, ²Agroecología, Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, Chapingo, Mexico

Summary: The Chapingo Organic Market (TOCh) began as a proposal to link organic production and the local consumption of healthy foods in the surroundings of the University in November 2003. In 2005, efforts began to certify the products, conforming the first nationwide effort to achieve participative certification (PC).

The investigation documented, through 5 case studies, the main strengths and weaknesses of (PC) based on the national organic guidelines.

The committee incorporates producers, consumers, and researchers. Some of the strengths found are valuable exchanges amongst producers and the certification committee, strict revisions so the products offered in the market comply with requirements, and those that do not comply are removed.

Some of the limitations are a lack of awareness regarding some sections of the regulations for their application (composting and labeling). The cost of volunteer work for certification was 528.45 dolares, and a total of 15,325 per year.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Participative Guarantee Systems, Agroecology, Lokal Market

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1301

GROUP CERTIFICATION – KEY FACTORS FOR SUCCESS

Beate Huber¹, Florentine Meinshausen², Toralf Richter¹, Johan Blockeel³

¹International Cooperation, FiBL, Frick, ²FiBL Consultant, Independent, Zurich, ³Socio-economic department, FiBL, Frick, Switzerland

Summary: About 80% of the world's organic producers are smallholders in low and middle income countries, for whom individual certification would be unaffordable and administratively too complex to manage. Group certification was originally developed to empower smallholders and improve their livelihoods by giving them access to the organic premium market.

The benefits that producers receive from certification are key factors for the success of collective certification schemes, the improvement of practices and for long-term compliance.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: access to markets, Grower Groups, Internal Control Systems, Smallholders, trade partnerships

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-740

BADABON HARVEST - MANGROVES TO MAIN STREET

Sandip Kar¹, Mallika Singh¹, Ajanta Dey²

¹Greener Rural Initiatives (P) Ltd., ²Nature Environment Wildlife Society, Kolkata, India

Summary: The marginal farmers of Sundarban Mangroves are highly dependent on their ecosystem for survival with limited livelihood options available - subsistence farming, fishing and honey collection.

It is an irony that in a geography blessed with abundant natural capital that can be monetized, most of the families are living below the UN defined poverty line (USD 1.90) with per capita daily income of USD 0.06 - USD 1.24.

Along with regular threats of periodic storms, man-animal conflict, cyclones and tidal surges the low income of the families also makes them vulnerable to various social evils, including, human trafficking.

The incubator (NEWS), working to protect the Mangroves for over a decade now, has inculcated a keen sense of ownership and association in the local community and assisted these farmers to come together and incorporate a Farmer Producer Organization (Badabon Farmers Producer Company Limited – brand “Badabon Harvest”).

They then partnered with social business accelerator (GRINS) to help monetize the natural capital by connecting this initiative to meet the rising demand for clean, honest, organically cultivated farm produce in the Kolkata market.

This submission focusses on using this connect as an engine for community development and highlight the use of innovative models and technology to strengthen its supply chain.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: climate change, Organic 3.0, organic consumer, organic farming, Jeevamrut, Amritpani, Recycling of farm waste, sustainable development goals, sustainable sourcing

Topic 1 - Experiences and innovations for a continuous improvement in reducing the environmental impacts of the production processes

OWC2020-SUP-771

VOLUNTEERS PROMOTING INCOME AND NUTRITION OF RURAL WOMEN IN JUMLA

Ghanashyam Nagarkoti*¹ and Rural Service Provider of Nutrition in Mountain Agro ecosystem (NMA)

¹Programme Management, Surya Social Service Society, Jumla, Nepal

Summary: In Jumla, farmers are provided technical knowledge, skill and input for growing local bean. They are practically coached on improved cultivation practice of bean: seed collection, sowing in line, staking, legume-cereal crop rotation, harvesting, processing and post-harvest handling. They are supported with different local varieties of bean, earlier farmers used to plant mixed varieties.

Besides, a demonstration plot of bean cultivation is also established to disseminate the practical knowledge. Farmers select and retain seeds from their own harvest for next season, thus avoiding costs, ensuring their access to seeds and making them independent from external supply.

From this practice, a pure variety of seed be at disposal of smallholder farmer at the time of sowing to mitigate effects of variable production and climate conditions and to make farming and food systems more resilient.

High consumer demand for the black bean at markets outside Jumla increased the farmer interest in its cultivation. Improved farming methods e.g. making use of stakes to let beans trail, which avoids fungal diseases, production of organic pesticides, implementation of nutrient cycling methods and climate adaptation have led to yield increase up to 3 times.

A local market outlet is promoting nutrient-based marketing. Being a high-value crop, marginalized farmers are benefited.

Thus, promoting the cultivation of indigenous crops and linking farmers to markets has multiple benefits for both the farmer and consumer. These include increasing farmer income and meeting consumer demand for locally grown, nutritious food.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Climate smart agriculture, High Value commodity, Participatory Market system Development

FOOD QUALITY ISSUES

Topic 2 - Food / Non-Food Processing: How to maintain/improve the quality and safety of products? How to make healthy products?

OWC2020-SUP-209

RMT ACTIA TRANSFOBIO - A NATIONAL THEMATIC NETWORK FOR TECHNICAL ADVICE ON ORGANIC PROCESSING

Rodolphe Vidal*¹, Solenne JOURDREN¹ and RMT ACTIA TRANSFOBIO

¹ITAB - Pôle Qualités et Transformation, ITAB, Paris cedex 12, France

Summary: A NETWORK OF EXPERTS DEDICATED TO THE FOOD AND AGRICULTURE INDUSTRY

Joint technological networks (Réseaux mixtes technologiques, RMT) are a new form of scientific and technical partnership established and supported by the French Ministry responsible for Food, and coordinated by Actia for the food industry.

COLLECTIVE RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES

In order to consolidate knowledge, the RMT is developing expertise on:

- the formulation of organic products (additives, processing aids, flavourings, and microbiological preparations) and alternative solutions;
- best practices in food processing and the best available technologies that are compatible with the guiding principles of organic farming;
- producing organic products that meet consumers' expectations.

A FORUM FOR SYNERGY AND DISCUSSION

Designed to popularise, communicate and disseminate technical advances, ensuring they are both usable and used as quickly and effectively as possible by all operators.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: assessment, Food system, Organic principles, processing technologies, technical and regulatory advices

Topic 2 - Food / Non-Food Processing: How to maintain/improve the quality and safety of products? How to make healthy products?

OWC2020-SUP-223

ULTRA-PROCESSING ALSO NEGATIVELY AFFECTS ORGANIC FOODS: WHICH SOLUTIONS?

Anthony Fardet*¹, Edmond Rock¹

¹Unité de Nutrition Humaine, INRA, Saint-Genès-Champanelle, France

Summary: When highly consumed, ultra-processed foods (UPFs) are associated with significant increased risks of chronic diseases, but also with degradation of food system sustainability. Unfortunately, organic foods are not immune to ultra-processing. They may represent up to 27% of sales in organic stores.

To address this capital issue, we developed the Golden 3Vs' Rules for protecting human health, animal biodiversity and welfare, environment (climate, pollution, deforestation...), socioeconomics, culinary traditions, and small farmers ; *i.e.*, : 1) "Végétal" for favoring Plant-based foods ; 2) "Vrai" for favoring Real food; and 3) "Varié" for Varied. In addition, the holistic technological Siga score (according to food degree of processing) allows, for Rule 2, identifying UPFs.

The 3Vs' Rules and Siga score may be important levers to improve food system sustainability, notably via the development of organic agriculture, which is holistic by nature.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Food system, Organic foods, Sustainability, The 3Vs' Golden Rules, Ultra-processing

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-511

THE RÉSEAU MANGER BIO (NETWORK EATING ORGANIC): HOW COLLECTIVE CATERING CAN DEVELOP ORGANIC AND ITS QUALITIES

Eric Grunewald*¹, Vincent Roze²

¹Réseau Manger Bio, valence, ²Réseau Manger Bio, Sainte Luce, France

Summary: Collective catering in France is a cultural exception, perhaps almost unique in the world, since local authorities (town halls, departments, regions) have the responsibility to provide the citizens for whom they are responsible (students, children, school children, students, elderly,..) meals including the meridian break, which is also a strong citizenship lever.

The Réseau Manger Bio and the various players that compose it are guarantors of this social utility.

Collective catering is also an important development lever for organic production, which was completely absent from the sector 15 years ago. For 10 years the Réseau Manger Bio has created a unique business model in this sector, which combines long and short supply chains, to secure supplies and relocate food.

The platforms that make up the Réseau Manger Bio have put producers at the heart of their governance and make sure to move towards an increasingly fair trade to the end by involving consumers in governance.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: collective catering, fair trade, local authorities

Topic : Experiences and innovations for the continuous reduction of environmental impacts in production processes

OWC2021-SUP-1402

CLEANING AND DISINFECTION IN ORGANIC PROCESSING FACILITIES: A REGULATORY CHALLENGE

Auteur: Bernard Lignon, SYNABIO

Summary: In the summary, there should be a short background, the main chapter, and core messages and conclusions. It should be understandable without the rest of the paper.

Dans le résumé, il devrait y avoir un bref arrière-plan, le chapitre principal et les principaux messages et conclusions. Cela devrait être compréhensible sans le reste du papier.

In the current European organic regulation, cleaning and disinfection(C&D) products are only regulated for animal production. According to the new 848/2018 regulation, the vegetable and food processing sectors will be concerned too. A positive list for C&D products should come into force the first January 2024 in order to use more ecological C&D products.

This regulatory approach is consistent with the organic principles, but it is a real challenge for several reasons such as the general regulation on C&D products, the technical complexity of C&D products, the lack of compulsory list for the composition of C&D products and the food safety obligations.

SYNABIO has set up realistic, scalable and auditable criteria to fulfill the provisions of the organic regulation. We have carried out a survey at European level to assess the feasibility of our proposal. It now has to be tested by organic companies and discussed with the commission and the C&D industry.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords:

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1050

GOTS 6.0 - ECOLOGY AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY WITH TRACEABILITY FROM FIELD TO FASHION

Claudia Kersten*¹

¹Managing Director, Global Standard gemeinnützige GmbH, Stuttgart, Germany

Summary: The Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) is the stringent voluntary global standard for the entire post-harvest processing of organic fibres with more than 2.2 million people working in more than 5.800 certified operations in more than 60 countries.

We would like to share learnings, actual requirements as result of the revision process to GOTS 6.0 and challenges regarding the future, including

- Development of GOTS from 2006-2020 – a continuous evolution from a harmonization process to the leading organic textile processing standard
- Description of the Revision Process and New Criteria in GOTS 6.0
- OWC 2017 - outcomes of the GOTS Preconference – how we worked on it
- Central Database - on the way to real time traceability
- Tools like Water Energy Monitor
- GOTS and the SDGs
- GOTS and international recognition
- Challenges
- A view to the future

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: GOTS From Field to Fashion, GOTS to fulfill SDGs, Integrity Textiles, Organic Textiles, Processing Organic Fibres, Traceability of Organic Textiles

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1086

UPGRADING THE ORGANIC STANDARDS FOR COCOA PRODUCTION – AGROFORESTRY SUBSTANTIALLY IMPROVE SUSTAINABILITY OF (ORGANIC AND CONVENTIONAL) COCOA PLANTATIONS

Monika Schneider*¹, Johanna Rüegg¹, Laura Armengot Martinez¹

¹International Cooperation, FiBL, Frick, Switzerland

Summary: Cocoa is increasingly produced in monocultures, while traditionally the shade tolerant crop is farmed in agroforestry systems. Cocoa monocultures yield more cocoa but total yield in agroforestry is higher as well as the return on labour. Agroforestry has a higher climate change adaptation and mitigation potential than monoculture.

We have evidence from a 12 year systems comparison trial and participatory on-farm research in Bolivia, that cocoa agroforestry systems are a viable alternative to monocultures and increase sustainability. We found, that even conventionally managed agroforestry systems perform better in many indicators than organic monocultures.

We advocate for an update of the organic standard for cocoa with the inclusion of agroforestry systems; to keep up with other sustainability standards and to ensure that organic agriculture promotes food security in producing areas, increasing diversification and resilience on farm level.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: agroforestry systems, Cocoa, Long-term experiment, research, sustainable development goals, systems research

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1087

NATURLAND STANDARD FOR INSECT BREEDING- A TRIAL YEAR WITH INNOVAFEED

Annabel Schuhn*¹, Chloe Phan Van Phi², Franzsika Patzwall¹

¹Naturland e.V., Gräfelfing, Germany, ²Innovafeed, Paris, France

Summary: With a growing global deficit in high quality proteins, protein production will be one of the key issues of the upcoming decades.

The situation is particularly precarious in Europe, where today 80% of crop protein is imported (mostly soybean meal). Insects, thanks to their ability to convert low-value biomass into high quality animal proteins and reintroduce them in the food chain, is emerging as an excellent solution to address this nutritional challenge.

To support alternative protein sources, Naturland implemented a guideline for organic insect breeding. In addition to being a sustainable alternative to fishmeal, insects are also part of the natural diet of fish, in particular salmonids.

In cooperation with InnovaFeed, a leading insect producer in France, a trial year has been running to see if the Naturland insects standards were applicable in practice. InnovaFeed is a biotech company that produces a new source of protein from insect rearing for animal feed and aquaculture.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: insects, protein sources, standards

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1127

EXPERIENCES WITH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PRIVATE STANDARDS FOR A SUSTAINABLE USE OF WATER RESOURCES BY BIO SUISSE AND NATURLAND AND AN OUTLOOK BEYOND STANDARDS AND CERTIFICATION

Alexander Koch¹, Carole Nordmann²

¹International department, Naturland, Gräfelfing, Germany, ²Sustainability, Bio Suisse, Basel, Switzerland

Summary: Water risks and water crisis are a huge challenge for agriculture and the organic movement. The organic farmer associations Naturland and Bio Suisse are strongly committed to sustainability and therefore also to the sustainable use of water resources.

Approximately 5 years ago both farmer associations have incorporated requirements for the sustainable use of water in their standards.

At the OWC 2020 an evaluation of the experiences with the implementation of the standards will be done. Achievements, challenges and faced obstacles will be reflected. Conclusions and an outlook for the coming years will be presented. This includes also questions beyond standards and certification, such as:

- · What can water standards achieve? Where are the limits of water standards and certification?
- · What additional measures are needed to deal with water risks and water crisis?
- · What further steps can be appropriate to promote the sustainable use of water in agriculture?

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Standards, Sustainable use of water resources, Water risks

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1215

PUBLIC AND PRIVATE STANDARDS ARE COMPLEMENTARY, BUT STRONG RELIABLE, TRANSPARENT GUARANTEES ARE THE COMMON NECESSARY GROUNDS TO DEVELOP ORGANIC AGRICULTURE

Laure Rolland¹, Philippe Thomazo*², Michel Reynaud³

¹ECOCERT EXPERT CONSULTING, ²ECOCERT, L'Isle Jourdain, ³ECOCERT, L'Isle-Jourdain, France

Summary: The speaker will present contextual elements related to standards' benefits and strengths for the development of organic activities. The main issues concerning the plurality and explosion of specifications on agricultural practices will also be reminded.

The core message will be presented in 3 parts:

1. Public standards must constitute the foundation for defining and respecting practices that correspond to the principles of organic farming.

2. Private standards are useful as complementary to the regulatory base on organic agriculture practices

3. The control systems of these specifications must provide reliable and transparent guarantees

Conclusions will encourage the development of public and private standards in a complementary and not competitive approach in order to support the evolution of practices that respect organic principles.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Eu organic legislation, Guarantee Systems, Private standards, Public standards

IMPROVING SUSTAINABILITY IN ORGANIC CHAINS, ESPECIALLY BIODIVERSITY

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1436

ALTER ECO IVORY COAST CHOCOLATE: AN INNOVATIVE ORGANIC, AGROFORESTRY AND FAIRTRADE COCOA SUPPLY CHAIN AIMING TO CONSERVE THE CLASSIFIED FOREST

Damien François*¹

¹Agri-chains, Bjorg Bonnetterre et Compagnie, Saint Genis Laval, France

Summary: Organic farming is a response to sustainability issues, but it does not cover all of them. To accelerate the ecological transition, it is necessary to go beyond organic specifications by considering factors such as biodiversity, CO₂, ethics. BBCIE seeks to integrate it into the monitoring of its raw material supply chains, based on criterias such as transparency, long-term partnerships, as well as agroecological practices and socio-economic benefits.

Alter Eco Fairtrade and Organic chocolate bar from Ivory Coast, launched in 2018, is a good illustration of it. In a context of farmers livelihood and environmental deterioration, the cocoa sourcing project aims at building a virtuous link between forest conservation, cocoa production and economical sustainability, with PCBM cooperative.

In addition to the development and organic premium, it's been decided to add an innovative premium for the Environmental Services provided by farmers committed to maintain a forest cover into their field.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Forest conservation, Ivorian cocoa, Environmental Service Premium, Fair for Life, organic sustainable partnership

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-499

BIOCOOP, BEEF FARMERS AND NATURALISTS: A PARTNERSHIP FOR LOCAL SOURCING AND BIODIVERSITY ADDED VALUE

Stéphanie Yardin¹ on behalf of Breeders - Biocoop - LPO Vendée

¹Biocoop, Challans, France

Summary: In the territory of Marais breton (north-west of Vendée, France), 4 partners have launched a meat store supply project which not only aims to guarantee a local and organic food to customers, but also to preserve domestic and wild biodiversity.

The 4 partners are: 2 biocoop stores (with retail butcher shops), an association of breeders and a nature conservation association.

The project aims to improve the wildlife on farms, to promote the Maraîchine cow (the local breed) and to communicate with consumers on positive or negative impacts of their consumption.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: biodiversity added value, endangered breeds, local sourcing, wildlife

Topic 1 - Experiences and innovations for a continuous improvement in reducing the environmental impacts of the production processes

OWC2020-SUP-959

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF ORGANIC CARROT PRODUCTION AND SUPPLY IN SWEDEN

Techane Bosona*¹, Girma Gebresenbet¹ and SusOrganic project

¹Energy and technology, Swedish university of agricultural sciences, Uppsala, Sweden

Summary: This paper presents the results of life cycle analysis (LCA) of fresh and dried organic carrot produced and supplied in Sweden. Cumulative energy demand (CED) and climate change impact have been investigated using cradle-to-consumer gate approach. The functional unit (FU) was 1 ton of fresh product at farm.

The major life cycle stages were agricultural production, post-harvest process, and transport. The total CED values were 2.64 GJ and 6.67 GJ per FU for fresh and dried carrot respectively. Regarding climate change impact, the values were 121 kg CO₂ eq and 111 kg CO₂ eq per FU for fresh and dried carrot respectively.

The drying process increased CED but reduced the climate change impact. In addition to reducing climate change impact, the drying process increases shelf life and selling price.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Cumulative Energy Demand; Organic carrot; Carrot drying; Life cycle analysis

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-987

AGROBIODIVERSITY AND SCHOOL CANTEENS FOR THE RESILIENCE OF PACIFIC FOOD SYSTEMS

Clement Gandet¹, Julie Ferrand²

¹Climat Change and Environmental Sustainability Division, Pacific Community (SPC), ²Animatrice, Chambre d'agriculture NC, Noumea, New Caledonia

Summary: The PROTEGE project pursues the goal of supporting sustainable and resilient development in a context of climate change within European Pacific territories. Several actions of PROTEGE aim at upgrading traditional agrobiodiversity (food and service) which has undergone significant erosion in recent decades to strengthen food security and population's health.

Collaborative work is currently being conducted with farmers to demonstrate both production and resilience gains achieved through maintaining a wide variety of traditional Oceanian food plants brought by the different waves of immigration.

This work also involves school canteens to bring back agricultural products that have been abandoned, through beneficial and appetizing recipes. The composition of plates, especially for school children, with neglected local products, out of fashion, becomes another tool to protect biodiversity.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: agrobiodiversity, PACIFIC FOOD SYSTEM, School canteen, traditional knowledge, food system, organic agriculture

Topic : Experiences and innovations for the continuous reduction of environmental impacts in production process

OWC2021-SUP-1404

BIODIVERSITY: INDICATORS FOR BETTER INSIGHT INTO ALL STAGES OF ORGANIC VALUE CHAINS

Auteur: Mathilde GSELL, CSR coordinator, Synabio

Summary * Safeguarding biodiversity is a major issue when it comes to global food security. Biodiversity loss figures are becoming more and more alarming. For example, nearly 80% of Europe's insect population has disappeared over the past 30 years.

The organic agriculture model represents a solid basis for protecting biodiversity. But as species continue to disappear and scientific knowledge in this area advances, it is essential for our sector to continue taking its practices beyond the requirements of EU regulations on organic farming.

Working closely with 10 organic companies and several environmental NGOs over the past year, Synabio, the French trade union for organic businesses, has identified 18 biodiversity-related progress indicators for organic supply chains (production, processing and distribution) and will be presenting them along with some goals to reach by 2023 and 2030.

This presentation will include a specific example of a best practice with an overview of the partnership between Biolait and the Ligue de Protection des Oiseaux (a bird protection league).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Organic / biodiversity / measure of progress / environment

STANDARDS FOR TRANSITION / TOOLS TO BOOST LOCAL DEVELOPMENT

Topic 3 - Transmission – education for an organic planet

OWC2020-CUL-667

BOOSTING ORGANICS BY ENHANCING KNOW-HOW IN FOOD PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

Sari Autio*¹, Maarit Mäki², Riitta Kaipainen³, Marja-Riitta Kottila⁴, Sari Iivonen⁵

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Summary: In the Luomubuumi project, our aim was to develop know-how and tools to support the production and marketing of Finnish organic food. We co-operated with regional projects within the food sector by organising workshops across the country, where the participants could discuss their product ideas among their peers and encounter inspiring examples of branding organic foodstuffs.

The workshops supported social learning by offering an arena for networking of small organic entrepreneurs, who often work alone and have few peers with whom to share their thoughts. The project delivers recommendations for the concepting and branding of organic products based on market surveys, needs of small enterprises and new raw materials.

Research-based knowledge about organic food was also disseminated in a popularized format in order to support the arguments for the unique characteristics of organic food. The outcomes are freely available as learning materials for anyone who wishes to obtain them.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: food products, know-how, marketing, new products, organics, social learning

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-1449

A SUCCESSFUL CASE OF INTEGRATING ORGANIC SMALL FARMERS INTO REGIONAL VALUE CHAINS THROUGH CONTRACT FARMING IN TAIWAN

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Summary: “Homemakers Union Consumers Co-op”, a well-known Eco-friendly Promotion Group (EPG) in Taiwan, operates by making contracts with organic growers. Although prices and purchase amounts are listed in the contract, the actual purchased amount can be adjusted by quality and market demand.

This system allow EPGs to bridge the gap between producers and consumers. Taiwanese government looks to encourage more small organic farmers to enter into contracts with EPGs by communicating contract details and helping farmers adopt advanced organic agri-technology, which benefit all parties.

We hope that Taiwanese experience is helpful to those practicing organic or eco-friendly farming in all member states, enabling them to excel in organic development.

Disclosure of Interest: None

Keywords: Eco-friendly Promotion Group (EPG), Value Chains, Contract Farming

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-827

BIO SUD OUEST FRANCE, A COLLECTIVE BRAND TO DEVELOP SUSTAINABLY THE REGIONAL ORGANIC SECTOR

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Summary: Interbio Nouvelle Aquitaine is the regional interprofessional association of organic organisms and operators. The main objectives of its actions are to promote and structure sustainably the regional organic sector.

Among all the tools developed by Interbio Nouvelle Aquitaine, Bio Sud Ouest France is a collective brand that can be considered as a strong one to help structuring regional organic streams.

Besides, Bio Sud Ouest France is an answer to consumers who are expecting organic brands to stand for more.

Indeed, it's a way of differentiating organic products and a step into fair trade. It permits to consume locally, to reduce the supply chain and to be solidar with producers of the territory. Finally, it is a way to build strong partnerships along the value chain, to obtain sustainably fair organic products.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: collective brand, consume locally, fair trade criterias, regional operators

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-923

HOW TAIWAN'S ORGANIC STANDARDS SUPPORT TRANSITIONING SMALLHOLDERS

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Summary: Four years after the implementation of national regulations, organic growth in Taiwan slowed down in 2011. For conversion of more farmers to organic practices, broad organic stakeholders advised the Council of Agriculture to reform public policies with supporting measures to promote organic development.

In 2018, Taiwan passed the Organic Agriculture Promotion Act and increased the total budget by allocating NT\$42 million a year to encourage organic farming.

The policy shall be to promote, propagate, develop further and implement the practice of organic agriculture in Taiwan in order to enrich the fertility of the soil, increase farm productivity, reduce pollution and destruction of the environment and prevent the depletion of natural resources.

The Government also introduced policies and programmes to support environmentally friendly farming and especially transitioning smallholders in cooperation with local NGOs. The number of participating farms is growing, as is their market share.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: eco-friendly, organic, policies, standards, support, transition

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-1058

HOW TERRES UNIVIA, A FRENCH ORGANISATION, CAN SUPPORT THE DEVELOPMENT OF OILSEED AND PULSE SECTOR?

Céline Le Guillou¹, Charlotte Canale¹

¹Terres Univia, Paris, France

Summary: The conversion of field crops to organic is very dynamic in France these last years. The organic areas of oilseeds, as well as pulses and dried vegetables areas, are increasing every year. This offer meets the growing consumption of organic products in France

Therefore, the demand for protein feed, and particularly oilmeals, is intensifying in France. A survey of seed collectors and first users (crushers and feed manufacturers) was realize to well understand the organic value chain and to give information to build an actions program like increasing of soya experimentation, study on protein content of our seeds...This study underlined that French organic pulses and sunflowerseeds' offer meet the demand of French industries. However, there is a lack of organic French rapeseed for edible oil and a lack of vegetable protein for feed (particularly French soymeal).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: French market, interbranch organisation, oilseed, pulse

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-1171

TECH&BIO: AN ORIGINAL CONCEPT TO TRANSFER OF TECHNIQUES AND SKILLS FOR TRANSITION TO MORE SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL AND FOOD SYSTEM AND TO DEVELOP ORGANIC AGRICULTURE

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Summary: Tech&Bio was created in 2007 by the french Chamber of agriculture with as main issues the transition to more sustainable agricultural and food system and the developpement of organic agriculture. Innovation, transfer of technique solution and skills between conventional and organic agriculture are the central concept of the brand.

It is neither a demonstration platform, nor a farm, nor a scientific congress, nor a trade show, nor an agricultural fair but a hybrid concept. Tech&Bio favors concrete approaches through field demonstrations, conferences on field innovations and research, testimonials from farmers and organization of the supply chain.

Initially for producers, the exhibition Tech&Bio has succeeded in involving all actors of the supply chain and territories.

Nowadays the exhibition is international, with nearly 60 partners, 350 exhibitors, 20,500 visitors and the brand Tech&Bio has been developed in France and is an international source of inspiration.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Connectedness, conversion to organic, Innovation, Supply Chain, technical and regulatory advices, Transfer

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1414

COMMENT INTEGRER LES VALEURS DE LA BIO POUR TOUS LES OPERATEURS D'UNE MEME FILIERE? ORIGINALITE STRUCTURATION FILIERES VIANDE ET LEGUMES EN BRETAGNE: CONTRACTUALISATION, CAHIER DES CHARGES RENFORCE, PLANIFICATION.

Julie Boulard¹, Goulven OILLIC¹ on behalf of IBB

¹Initiative Bio Bretagne, RENNES, France

Summary * In the summary, there should be a short background, the main chapter, and core messages and conclusions. It should be understandable without the rest of the paper.

It is interesting to compare 2 “north / north” trade experiences, which are innovations in terms of governance, having the common goal of transformation to create added value and find material balance. The 2 examples are Bio Breizh and Bio Direct, groups of vegetables producers and a pork producers.

The basis of the 2 systems is cooperation and mutual aid, to secure supply and not to be in competition. The 2 examples are complementary and different. The two producers organizations go beyond the organic specifications and are involved in the structuring of organic supply chains and show that the involvement of producers in the value chain creates added value and remunerative prices.

These exemplary partnerships influence beyond the Bio sphere and rebuild the groundwork for a more equitable distribution model.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: meat quality, sector structuring, value chain partnership, Vegetable production

Contribution text

THE ROLE OF THE AGRICULTURAL CO-OPERATIVE MODEL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMING

Editor: Clara Baudoin, testimony David Joubier organic farmer

Summary * In the summary, there should be a short background, the main chapter, and core messages and conclusions. It should be understandable without the rest of the paper.

The territory has been structured over the years by the Breton agricultural co-operative model. At a time when organic farming is questioning its ability to upgrade into a more accessible consumer model, it remains a generating value to many growers.

They chose to become members of a cooperative and contribute to its organic farming sectors growth. David Joubier is one of these organic farmers in Morbihan,

With sectors management organisation, the cooperative provides its producer members with good monitoring of their crops and breeding. With good expertise, innovation, advice from the technical support teams, each member can adopt more sustainable development practices. The co-operative governance model gives fair representation and defense of the producers' interests.

One major role of the co-operative is to provide good guidance of the territories. Producers can share experiences and know how. Also, the main national brands Paysan Breton and Daucy's involvement provides an extraordinary communication support helping growers putting the values of their profession and territory forward to consumers.

Keywords: Organic farming, agricultural Co-operative, sectors, members, producers, territory, co-operation, pooling, monitoring, development, quality, traceability, proximity, value,

LA FILIÈRE BIO, EVOLUTION ÉCONOMIQUE, OUTILS ET ENJEUX FINANCIERS

Auteur: Crédit Coopératif Stéphanie Perez

Summary * La Filière Bio a connu une évolution économique sans précédent durant les vingt dernières années, avec une transformation structurelle de ses secteurs en amont comme en aval, de l'agriculture, en passant par la transformation, à la distribution.

Les modes de consommation et les attentes des populations en matière de santé, et d'impact écologique ont évolué et sont un vecteur majeur de ces changements: démocratisation de la bio, essor des surfaces cultivables et des élevages certifiés bio, la filière Biologique est passée d'un marché de niche à un secteur situé au cœur des stratégies commerciales des entreprises.

Mais pour se développer, la filière Bio a besoin de capitaux et de solutions financières adaptées à ses besoins.

Quels sont les outils de financement à disposition des acteurs de la filière? Comment les besoins de la filière bio ont évolué et comment les organismes y répondent? Comment les structures coopératives sont un modèle favorable au développement de la filière?

Disclosure of Interest:

Keywords: **Economie, marché, finance, coopératives**

HOW TO IMPROVE ORGANIC INTEGRITY: CONTINUOUS CHALLENGES OF THIRD PARTY CERTIFICATION

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-1477

ENSURING ORGANIC INTEGRITY. AN ANALYSIS OF TOOLS AND STRUCTURES.

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¹communications management, ²director, organic services, Tutzing, Germany

Summary: This presentation will point out the potential dangers for the organic sector if fraud is not prevented efficiently. It will provide an evaluation of our current organic control system, reflecting on its strengths, weaknesses and limitations.

In this context, complementary solutions to prevent and fight fraud with organics will be analyzed. These include, amongst others, the European Commission's data tool TRACES, Blockchain, analytics and mass balance.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Certification, Fraud Prevention, Organic Integrity, Verification, Monitoring, Supply Chain, Continuous Improvement, ICT support tools, integrity of supply chain, Supply Chain, transparency

Topic 4: Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-579

ORGANIC FRAUD PREVENTION SOLUTIONS

Authors: Gwendolyn Wyard, Vice President of Regulatory & Technical Affairs, Organic Trade Association

Summary: As the organic industry has grown, so have occurrences of organic fraud. Organic fraud is defined as an intentional misleading or deceptive action carried out for illicit financial gain.

Fraudulent acts may include adulteration, substitution, falsified records, the deliberate mislabeling of goods, as well as false statements made in written or verbal form during the organic certification process, such as organic certification applications, the organic system plan, or during inspections.

Any way we look at it, organic fraud cannot be tolerated in the organic supply chain, inside or outside the United States. Anytime there is fraud anywhere in the organic system, it takes value out of the organic label and hurts organic farmers everywhere. Everyone plays a role in preventing organic fraud, including the private sector.

It is critical that organic businesses have robust systems and measures in place that adequately support the promise of providing organic products that people can trust.

Keywords: Fraud Prevention, Organic Integrity, Verification, Monitoring, Supply Chain, Continuous Improvement

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-723

THE ADDED VALUE OF THE THIRD-PARTY CERTIFICATION

Aurelie Quintin¹

¹EOCC European Organic Certifiers Council, Bruxelles, Belgium

Summary: Over the past decades, the control of organic products became more and more professional.

Third Party Certifiers (or Private Control Bodies) became a pillar of the control system. They verify and certify that each operator in the supply chain (farmers, processors, importers, retailers) applies correctly the rules, according to public or private standards.

What is the added value for an operator of being certified by a Control Body? What are the guarantees provided to the consumer?

The European Organic Certifiers Council (EOCC) will present how CBs work, how their own surveillance is organized, how the evolution of the organic farming requires a competent, impartial and independent control in order to guarantee, more than ever, consumers trust in the integrity of organic products.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Accreditation, Competence, Consumers trust, Inspection, Third Party certification

SEEDS AND OTHER FARM INPUTS: CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIONS

Topic 2 - A life-oriented paradigm to foster the organic movements

OWC2020-CUL-1403

A PARTNERSHIP FOR INDEPENDENCE AND BIODIVERSITY: FINANCING ORGANIC BREEDING AND SEED PRODUCTION BY THE SUPPLY CHAIN

Kunz Peter* ¹, Monika Baumann², Herbert Völkle², Federica Bigongiali²

¹Fund for crop plant development, ²Getreidezüchtung Peter Kunz, Feldbach, Switzerland

Summary: In the last forty years about one hundred new cereal and vegetable varieties have been developed by pioneers on biodynamic nurseries and released in the official variety catalogues through non-profit breeding initiatives. In southern Germany and Switzerland more than 65% of organic certified bread cereals grow from organic bred varieties, because they are superior to conventional varieties in quality and stability. These initiatives were supported by private donations, by several companies and some foundations (i.e. GLS Seed Fund). They achieve a high degree of professionalisation, but they are constantly threatened by underfunding and their growth is severely hampered. To change this, efforts must therefore be multiplied. We propose a new and simple financing model for organic breeding called crop per mille. All food chain partners can participate with one per mille of their turnover.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Financing organic breeding, Participation, value chain partnership

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-361

CAN CROWDSOURCING TECHNOLOGY REVOLUTIONIZE COLLABORATIVE BREEDING AND TESTING?

Nicolas Enjalbert¹, Julie Dawson²

¹SeedLinked, Viroqua, ²Horticulture, UW Madison, Madison, United States

Summary: In parallel to the world of centralized plant breeding, a fundamentally different model of agriculture is emerging, based on diversifying farms and building healthier & more resilient agro-ecosystems. However, 4 main barriers are still present: 1) A lack of adapted varieties, 2) low adoption of new varieties, 3) little access to varieties adapted to specific climatic or regional conditions, and 4) few options for farmers looking to source organic seeds.

The good news is that we have never been as connected as today, via the smartphone in our pocket.

We combine smartphone apps and farmer observations, following citizen science approach, to optimize seed performance predictors for small & medium sized farms.

Combining plant breeding and data science with software engineering we demonstrate that crowdsourcing variety performance aggregated by farmers and gardeners via intuitive apps can actually predict variety performance.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: seed breeding collaborative

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-841

SUPPLYING ORGANIC SEEDS IN FRANCE: A COLLECTIVE CHALLENGE

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Summary: The French Interprofessional Organisation for Seeds and Plants (GNIS) has implemented a series of collective initiatives involving technical institutes and organic farming operators aimed at promoting and accelerating the use of organic seeds.

These initiatives aim to eliminate technical barriers to seed production, improving market intelligence to be better able to supply it and to determine seed varieties best suited to organic farming.

At the same time, GNIS is funding national and international initiatives to promote conservation and access to cultivated plant biodiversity.

The ambition is to supply 95% of the market with organic seeds by 2025 and adapt a strong support and incentivising role towards seed producers.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: French, Gnis, INAO, seed

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1193

**GLOBAL RISE OF BIOPESTICIDES: CURSE OR WIN FOR THE ORGANIC SECTOR?
WILL AN INCREASED AVAILABILITY OF BIOPESTICIDES INCREASE THE USE OF
THOSE BIOPESTICIDES?
IS THERE A NEED FOR A NEW ORGANIC REGULATORY POLICY APPROACH?**

An Jamart¹, Lieven Delanote² and the Flemish farmers network of organic open field vegetables

¹BioForum Vlaanderen vzw, Antwerpen, ²Inagro, Roeselare, Belgium

Summary: The position of organic open field vegetable farmers in relation to an increasing availability of biopesticides becomes more and more ambiguous. There is a real need for resources and even a need for some more efficient alternatives to existing biopesticides in certain vegetables such as leek and cabbage to achieve the exigences in yield and quality of the organic market. There is also a concern that greater availability of biopesticides will lead to higher pressure to use them in conflict with the authentic organic farm system approach.

BioForum, the umbrella organisation for the organic sector in Flanders, conducted personal interviews and qualitative analysis within the value chain to analyse this dilemma. The results showlights how operating as an organic farmer in an overall conventional value chain, distribution and retail system forces farmers towards conventionalization and away of a more agroecological approach and the organic principles set forward by IFOAM.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: agroecology, biopesticides, conventionalisation, upscaling

Topic 2 - Farmers empowerment and autonomy on their farm and on the market

OWC2020-FAR-1298

ABIO PARTICIPATORY GUARANTEE SYSTEM (SPG) AND CARIOCA ORGANIC FAIRS CIRCUIT: COLLECTIVE BUILDING STRATEGIES THAT LEVERAGED THE PRODUCTION AND SUPPLY OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN RIO DE JANEIRO

Maria Fernanda D. A. C. Fonseca¹, Ana Paula P. D. Siqueira², Lucia Helena M. D. Almeida², Cristina D. B. Ribeiro³, Daniel V. D. S. Dias¹

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Summary: The Association of Biological Farmers of the State of Rio de Janeiro (ABIO) has always maintained, since its constitution, a strong relationship with conscious consumers through the direct sale of its Associates' products, starting with the Health Fair in 1985, one of the first organic fairs in Brazil, as well as sales to its own store and to consumer groups, until culminating in the design and implementation of the Carioca Organic Fairs Circuit (CCFO).

The preparation of the CCFO proposal took place in parallel with the Association's decision to implement its Participatory Guarantee Scheme (GSP) in 2007 and both strengthened and grew concomitantly.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: conformity assessment, organic guarantee system, street market

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1001

A REGIONAL ORGANIC STANDARD AND A LARGE CHOICE OF GUARANTEE SYSTEMS IN THE PACIFIC

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¹Climat Change and Environmental Sustainability Division, Pacific Community (SPC), ²Chambre d'agriculture NC, Noumea, ³Bio Caledonia PGS, La Foa , New Caledonia

Summary: The Pacific Countries and Territories adopted a common organic standard in 2007: "Organic Pasifika". The provisions of the Standard take into account both local agricultural traditions and the two global organic standards, IFOAM IBS and Codex Alimentarius. Thus, the adoption of this standard should promote access to organic certification of family farms that are predominant in the region.

Products bearing "Organic Pasifika" mark are certified to the Pacific Organic Standard by an internationally accredited and POETCom approved certifying body or through a robust, POETCom registered Participatory Guarantee System. The States and Territories have therefore made the choice to propose a plurality of guarantee systems to farmers in order to allow all to value their organic practices.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Participatory Guarantee System (PGS), Regional organic standard

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1152

FROM SUPPLY-CHAIN TO COMMUNITY. ECORNATURASI'S COMMITMENT FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A PARTICIPATORY GUARANTEE SYSTEM AMONG THE FARMERS BELONGING TO ITS ITALIAN SUPPLY CHAIN.

Alessandra De Cesero¹, Carlo Murer*¹

¹EcorNaturaSi, San Vendemiano, Italy

Summary: EcorNaturaSi, Italian distributor of organic products, is devoting energies and resources for the implementation of a Participatory Guarantee System involving farmers, shopkeepers and the clients of its shops. The logic behind the implementation of a PGS, for EcorNaturaSi, is the desire to create a connection between the people who produce the food and the people who eat the food.

The idea is to turn the linear concept of supply chain, which sees farmers and consumers far apart on the two opposite extremes of the chain, into a model where farmers and consumers get to know each other.

The key element for the Participatory Guarantee System to work is to trigger the inherent need of people to know where the food comes from in order to have a feeling of trust and safety toward the food they eat.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Community, NaturaSi, Organic, Participatory Guarantee System

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1232

PARTICIPATORY GUARANTEE SYSTEM FOR BROGNA SHEEP ASSOCIATION IN LESSINIA (VR)

Antonio Compagnoni*¹, Marcello Volanti¹, Raffaele Zanolli², Francesco Solfanelli²

¹ICEA, BOLOGNA, ²Scienze Agricole, Alimentari e Ambientali, UNIPM, Ancona, Italy

Summary: Between October 2018 and September 2019 through the iSAGE H20 EU research project, it was carried out this innovation case study.

This innovation can bring more economical sustainability to the farm while performing more environmentally friendly practices and improving animal welfare. It can also improve the social sustainability of a particular farming system better connecting the producers with local processors and market actors (butchers, restaurants), consumers / citizens / tourists and local authorities.

Unit of analysis: The association of the Brogna sheep that includes 40 members: 25 farmers, 10 processors (butchers, restaurants, wool workshops) 3 technicians (1 agronomist 2 veterinaries) and some consumers/supporters.

The different steps of the process to implement the PGS were monitored and recorded. Data and information were collected after the innovation introduction: through interviews with members understanding their willingness to adopt the new system.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: None

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-733

GROWING ORGANIC TRUST - IMPROVING CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT IN ORGANIC PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

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¹Alliance for Organic Integrity, Chapel Hill, United States

Summary: If there is no integrity, there will be no value to share. The Alliance for Organic Integrity has been established with the ultimate goal of enhancing the availability and quality of the organic guarantee being provided to consumers.

Its mission is to educate all stakeholders about best practices, to develop tools for preventing fraud and to share these tools and educational components with all those involved.

This paper will explore an example of the projects being undertaken, the tools being developed, and the way we intend these will be taken up and used by the wider organic community.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Accessibility, Communication, Control, Fraud prevention, Innovation, Training

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-1046

ORGANIC AGRICULTURE IS A POTENTIAL LEVER FOR TECHNOLOGICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL BREAKTHROUGHS IN FOOD SECURITY IN AFRICA

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Summary: The development of Organic Agriculture (AB) is at the heart of controversies related to the technological orientations in agriculture that satisfy agronomic, economic, social and environmental objectives. By mobilizing several studies recently conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), we propose to document these controversies.

We question the relevance of the certification standards defined by the industrialized countries in SSA and explore the emergence of new standards better adapted to the regional contexts. Our work reveals a knowledge gap on comparative performance between AB (certified and non-certified) and conventional agriculture (CA).

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Africa, Elicitation method, food security, Innovation, Organic Agriculture, Traditional Farms, Seeds, Fertilizers, Protection, Harvest, Processing & Marketing

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-1048

ORGANIC MARKET AND SECTOR DEVELOPMENT IN UKRAINE

Tobias Eisenring*¹, Thomas Bernet¹

¹International Cooperation, FiBL Switzerland, Frick, Switzerland

Summary: Agriculture is an important pillar of the Ukrainian economy. A survey conducted by FiBL in 2018 shows that stakeholders of the Ukrainian organic sector are convinced that organic farming bring not only environmental but also economic benefits in the longer term. In arable crop production, meaningful export opportunities are created that enhance Ukraine's agricultural competitiveness while protecting environmental resources.

Yet, in contrast to organic berry and vegetable production, employment effects and income generation is less pronounced in arable crop production. Overall, Ukraine's potential for further organic sector development—for both export and the domestic market—justify continued public investments into this sector.

The new national organic legislation, in force since August 2019, is an important milestone contributing to trust and strengthening the sector.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Organic market and sector development Ukraine

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-1123

ACCESS TO MARKETS: A ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY

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¹Agriculture, ²Agriculture, local Government, New Taipei City, Taiwan

Summary: “Creating marketing channels at first” is the spirit of agriculture policy of New Taipei City (NTPC) Government. With the base of urban consuming ability created by 4 million population and contractual farming, it creates various sales channels for farmers to ensure the sales of agricultural products.

At the same time, through training, it fosters the ability of young farmers to utilize digital marketing and to manage recreational agriculture, which increases the value added during the production process.

After becoming a member of IFOAM Asia in July 2019, NTPC cofounds CEIOMA (Center of Excellence for Intelligent Organic Marketing in Asia) with IFOAM Asia, it aims to become the base leading the development of organic agriculture in Asia by marketing.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: contractual farming, local authorities, marketing channel, policies

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-732

THE AVENIR BIO FUND AND THE CLUB DES FINANCEURS: TWO TOOLS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FRANCE'S ORGANIC SUPPLY CHAINS

Florent GUHL*¹, Anne BASSET²

¹director, ²Agence BIO, MONTREUIL, France

Summary: The structuring of organic supply chains is a crucial issue for all stakeholders (producers, processors and distributors).

Such structuring needs to involve a contractual relationship between the operators (upstream and downstream), fair allocation of value-added across all the links in the chain and the development of products aligned with consumer expectations.

In France, Agence Bio, a public interest grouping (GIP), works to enhance the structure of organic supply chains through the use of two public policy tools: the *Avenir Bio* fund and the *Club des Financeurs*.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: CONSULTATION, DISCUSSIONS, partnership, value allocation

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-888

NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES DRIVING SUPPLY CHAIN COLLABORATION IN RETAIL AND FOOD SERVICE: THE CASE OF DENMARK

Paul Holmbeck*¹

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Summary: In Denmark, a range of very effective political policies at the national and local level are driving supply chain collaboration on market development in both retail and food service, as well as export.

Among the policies are goals for doubling organic sales on the home market and for exports, investment in NGO supply chain facilitation and market development, an organic export academy, an organic school for food service companies, support to cities converting procurement to minimum 60 percent organic, and an education fund for cities training kitchen workers in organic conversion.

The central messages are that organic food policy works. By supporting supply chain collaboration on market development, product development, training, conversion of public kitchens, and consumer awareness, political policies are driving market growth.

Denmark has now the highest organic market share (over 12 percent) and growth of 15-25 percent annually in different sectors: retail, food service, export.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: collaboration, market development, policies, public procurement, Retail, Supply Chain

Topic 3 - Develop organic and sustainable plant and animal production, food and non-food systems

OWC2020-STA-1189

INCREASING TRANSPARANCY IN THE ORGANIC INPUT SECTOR: THE FIBL INPUT LISTS.

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Summary: Inputs are materials, which may be used in agriculture or food processing, such as fertilizers, soil conditioners, plant protection products, cleaning agents and disinfectants products for the control of animal parasites, feed materials, feed additives, food additives and food processing aids.

Such materials are frequently applied on farm and food processing level respectively, to optimally meet the needs of crops and animals and to keep them healthy. For organic production, the Annexes to Reg. (EC) No 889/2008 list the substances, which may be used as inputs in EU organic production.

However, inputs are mostly complex mixtures of different components that often contain a range of different co-formulants. As inputs are not subject to compulsory inspection and certification, it is almost impossible to determine whether an input only contains authorized materials, introducing a substantial risk for organic farmers as well as for the organic sector as a whole.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Eu organic legislation, Fertilizers, Input, plant protection products, plant strengtheners, transparency

Topic 1 - Experiences and innovations for a continuous improvement in reducing the environmental impacts of the production processes

OWC2020-SUP-1173

COMMENT NOUS TRADUISONS LA BIO DANS NOS CUISINES OU POURQUOI JE NE VEUX PLUS OUVRIR DE RESTAURANT

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Summary: Comment nous traduisons La BIO dans nos cuisines ou pourquoi je ne veux plus ouvrir de restaurant

Lorsque j'ai ouvert RESSOURCES, un petit laboratoire de cuisine ouvrant directement sur la rue et proposant une cuisine à emporter, l'intention était de tenter quelque chose coute que coute.

L'ampleur du désastre écologique annoncé m'a conduit à remettre en cause tout ce que je savais de mon métier pour mettre mes compétences de cuisinière au service des calories disponibles.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Alimentation Durable, Cuisine bas-carbone, Cuisine écoresponsable, réappropriation du repas quotidien

Topic 3 - How to better share value along supply chains, how to go towards fair organic, how to improve the working conditions?

OWC2020-SUP-1206

COMBINATION OF TECHNICAL AND LOGISTICAL INNOVATIONS FOR POST-HARVEST TREATMENTS IN ORDER TO PERMIT THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIC HEMP AND THE ORGANIC PERFUMED, AROMATIC AND MEDICINAL PLANTS INDUSTRIES

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Summary: In order to diversify the crop rotations in organic agriculture, the organic hemp and the perfumed, aromatic and medicinal plants (PAM plants) industries are developing in the north east of France.

However, the drying processes of the hemp seeds and of the PAM plants appear to be a limiting factor to their development, linked with quality aspects necessary for human alimentation.

In this context, a European Innovation Partnership (EIP) project conducting by Bio en Grand Est aims first to create more versatile dryers for hems, PAM plants, protein crops and cereals; and second to elaborate an integrated logistic between the dryers and the dryer users through a collaborative digital platform.

The combination of technical and logistical innovations around the dryers should permit to lift the major restriction of the organic hemp and the PAM plants industries development.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: drying process, logistical innovation, organic hemp industry, perfumed, aromatic and medicinal plants industry, technical innovation

Topic 5 - Standards: their role to develop practices that respect organic principles

OWC2020-SUP-1217

DEVELOPMENT OF A STANDARD ATTESTING OF A VOLUNTARY APPROACH TOWARDS THE ORGANIC PRODUCTION OBJECTIVES AS SET IN THE (CE) N°834/2007 REGULATION: THE CASE OF YVES ROCHER'S AGROECOLOGICAL VALUE CHAIN.

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Summary: The organic European regulation guarantees that there was no use of chemicals; but the fundamental objectives of organic agriculture, dealing with respect of nature's systems, often lack control.

On the other hand, agroecology is a term that incorporates all the core values of organic farming (biodiversity, protection of land and consumers) whilst adding a holistic approach to it, with an emphasis on local networking, human connection and resilience of the systems.

Yves Rocher produces and buys organic plants for its cosmetic products. Deeply concerned with its birth land development in La Gacilly and with nature, the company tries to build a standard based on values and will to progress towards an agroecological ideal operation of the farm and the land, in addition to the fixed standards found in the organic label.

This approach raises questions, around the authenticity of classical organic supplying systems.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Agroecology, European regulation, Private firm, Standard

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-793

PRESENTATION OF THE “DEVELOPMENT GUIDE FOR THE ORGANIC FRUIT AND VEGETABLE MARKET”

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Summary: The French fresh fruit and vegetable inter-professional association which brings together all jobs in the field (from production to distribution) will publish, at the end of 2019, a “Development Guide for the Organic Fruit and Vegetable Market”.

This helpful guide, over 200 pages long, written by professionals in the field for professionals in the field, brings together all the information you need to know before transforming or developing your business into an organic one, for example: where you can find out about the changing market; where you can find information on regulations; who the reference organisations are; how to interact with other professions in the field; and how to spread the word about organic fruit and vegetables...

This guide also contains testimonials and feedback from professionals committed to developing the organic fruit and vegetable market.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: development, fresh, fruit, guide, organic, vegetable

Topic 6 - Development of pro-organic Policies along Value and Supply Chains

OWC2020-SUP-816

30% OR 50% OF ORGANIC: FAR-FETCHED ILLUSION OR CLOSE-TO-REAL?

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Summary: The organic agriculture sector is booming and increasingly developing in Europe throughout the last decade. However, no studies have been carried out so far regarding a 30% aim of organic agricultural production and retail sales by 2030.

This exploratory study shows that even if the evolution of these two parameters is very heterogeneous among different countries, the 30% aim seems to be realistic for some of them

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Agribusiness, Future, growth, Market, Political Agroecology

Topic 4 - Ensuring sourcing along supply chains

OWC2020-SUP-820

STRATEGY ANALYSIS OF THE FRENCH ORGANIC SPECIALISED RETAIL: WHAT IS THE ROLE OF LOCAL PRODUCTS?

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Summary: In France, the increasing demand on organic food has allowed the organic specialised retail to grow faster in the last decade.

Studies carried in Germany by Hempel (2015) and Hempel and Hamm (2016), show that organic-minded consumers care more about the local origin of products, and are willing to pay more for the local products.

Brown et al (2009) have shown that quality is the main key behind buying local products by French consumers. Hence, the local organic products have become a priority for the customer. The French sector being a dynamic market; the specialised organic retail contributes with 36% of the gross organic products sales (Agence Bio, 2018).

The objective of this paper is to analyse the strategic role of “local products” in organic specialised retail.

A survey on 106 organic specialised stores has been conducted during May and June 2019, in order to understand the importance of local products in organic food stores and the bulk selling of those products.

Disclosure of Interest: None Declared

Keywords: Food system, local foods, Retail, Supply Chain

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